

D3.5 Practice Abstracts – Batch 1

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ACRONYMS & ABBREVIATIONS

EU	European Union
LAG	Local Action Group
Project partners	
Galway	NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND GALWAY
TU Delft	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITEIT DELFT
TEAGASC	TEAGASC - AGRICULTURE AND FOOD DEVELOPMENT AUTHORITY
UNICAL	UNIVERSITA DELLA CALABRIA
LWL	LONGFORD WOMEN S LINK CLG
UTU	TURUN YLIOPISTO
UL	UNIVERZA V LJUBLJANI
CE	CONSULTA EUROPA PROJECTS AND INNOVATION SL
HNEE	HOCHSCHULE FUR NACHHALTIGE ENTWICKLUNG EBERSWALDE
ELARD	ASSOCIATION EUROPEENNE LEADER POURLE DEVELOPPEMENT RURAL
UOULU	OULUN YLIOPISTO
ECOLISE	RESEAU EUROPEEN POUR DES INITIATIVES COMMUNAUTAIRES SUR LES CHANGEMENTS CLIMATIQUES ET LE DEVELOPPEMENT DURABLE
MENDELU	MENDELOVA UNIVERZITA V BRNE
LNU	LINNEUNIVERSITETET
HLK	HOGSKOLAN FOR LARANDE OCH KOMMUNIKATION I JONKOPING - HLK SCHOOL OF EDUCATION AND COMMUNICATION

SUMMARY

The FLIARA project investigates women-led innovations in farming and rural areas in Europe. The aim of WP3 was to deepen the understanding of the pathways to success and the challenges facing female-led sustainability innovation in a) farming and b) rural areas.

Twenty national case studies were carried out in ten European countries (Czech Republic, Finland, Germany, Ireland, Italy, Netherlands, Romania, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden), resulting in the analysis of 200 women-led innovations (Sivini et al, 2024) and a comparative analysis of case studies was conducted (Roos et al., 2025).

The aim of this deliverable is to facilitate the dissemination of knowledge from the above analyses and includes 10 practice abstracts. They were drawn considering the FLIARA assessment framework (Farrell et al, 2023). This includes a three-pronged approach:

- 1) **innovation pathways.** Consider a number of stages (motivations of the innovations, constrains and favourable conditions, idea and preparations, concrete innovations, impact);
- 2) **innovation ecosystems.** These are considered holistic operational environments in which female-led innovations in rural areas and farms take place.
- 3) **mainstreaming** female-led innovations to explore innovation expansion.

The topics covered in the abstracts can be summarised by considering these three levels.

Innovation pathways

Motivations. Women have diverse motivations to innovate, and the economic one is not always the main one. In Finland and Sweden clearly emerge that the desire to realize a new idea is the powerful motivator as illustrated in practice abstract 1.

Constrains. One of the most relevant challenges faced by women innovators in farming and rural areas is related to accessing the finance needed to support innovation. Women innovators adapt and use many sources of finances. Possible improvements of existing finance supports are highlighted in practice abstract 2.

Favourable conditions. Networking is a clear key facilitator for women innovators in rural areas and farming. Practical recommendations to facilitate the access to networks are suggested in practice abstract 3.

Skills in digital communication as well as in the implementation of e-commerce are relevant characteristics of women innovators living and working in rural areas. Practical recommendations are given in practice abstract 4.

Concretisations and impact. Practice Abstract 5 focuses on multifunctional agriculture, which is a common characteristic of most women innovators in farming. On the one hand, this model makes it possible to diversify the income sources of the farm and, on the other hand, it allows women to develop different innovative services based on their personal skills and interests, be it recreational (e.g. escape rooms), educational (e.g. farm kindergarten) and/or social (e.g. cooking workshops).

Women innovators in farming show a high level of environmental awareness, which translates into the adoption of techniques that ensure soil health and animal welfare. Practical recommendations for improving support services and training in environmentally sustainable agriculture are outlined in Practice Abstract 6.

Women innovators in rural areas follow different paths to success. However, it is possible to highlight three successful strategies for achieving innovation in rural areas that are illustrated in Practice Abstract 7.

Innovation ecosystem

In order to avoid the imposter syndrome, which the analysis of the interviews revealed in several cases, it is necessary to build the confidence and self-esteem of rural women innovators. The practice abstract 8 outlines the practical steps to be taken.

Practice abstract 9 revolves around a supportive environment for women innovators in rural areas and farming that could be offered by the LEADER measure/interventions. The role of LAGs in supporting women has been highlighted by many interviewees.

Mainstreaming

Women-led innovations have a significant local impact. Scaling out through imitation seems to be a way to expand their sustainable innovations. Practice abstract 10 highlights successful mainstreaming strategies.

INTRODUCTION

This deliverable emerges from FLIARA Task 3.4. “Comparative analysis of the case studies by country and sustainability dimension”. All partners have been involved in this task.

The analysis considered the following 4 European macro-regions: Atlantic (coordinated by Galway), Nordic-Baltic (coordinated by LNU), Central and Eastern (coordinated by UL), and Mediterranean (coordinated by UNICAL) (see Table 1).

Table 1. Partners by macro-regional groups

No	Partner short name	Country	Macro Region	Coordinate
1	GALWAY	Ireland	Atlantic	X
2	TU Delft	Netherlands	Atlantic	
3	TEAGASC	Ireland	Atlantic	
4	LWL	Ireland	Atlantic	
5	HNEE	Germany	Atlantic	
1	LNU	Sweden	Nordic Baltic	X
2	UOULU	Finland	Nordic Baltic	
3	HLK	Sweden	Nordic Baltic	
4	UTU	Finland	Nordic Baltic	
1	UL	Slovenia	Central and Eastern	X
2	ECOLISE	Belgium/ covering Romania	Central and Eastern	
3	MENDELU	Czechia	Central and Eastern	
4	ELARD	Belgium/covering Romania	Central and Eastern	
1	UNICAL	Italy	Mediterranean	X
2	CE	Spain	Mediterranean	

Following the WP3 research guidelines (Sivini et al, 2023), the analysis has been developed through the following three steps:

- Each national group was tasked with feeding the preparation of the comparative report at a macro-regional level with information from an analysis at country level of the case studies, organised by the four sustainability innovation dimensions (environmental, economic, social and cultural).
- Comparative analysis within the four macro-regional groupings. The partner coordinating the work at macro-regional level prepared the comparative report with the support of the other teams (See table 1).
- Comparative analysis of emerging issues across the four regions to derive European level insights. UNICAL and LNU conducted this analysis.

To facilitate knowledge flows from this analysis and the outcomes of the 20 case studies (Task 3.3.), ten practice abstracts were drawn up.

Each coordinator (Galway, LNU, UL, UNICAL) was tasked to prepare two practice abstracts based on the analysis of women-led innovation in rural areas and in farming. In addition, UNICAL and LNU prepared two practice abstracts based on the European insights. The topics were discussed among the coordinators; in some cases, the practice abstracts contain indications that are common to all the investigated countries; in other cases, the reference is specific to certain macro-regions.

Looking at all ten practice abstracts, three topics come up more frequently than others. These are networking, different ways of accessing finance, and the vastness of the

impact of female-led innovation. Networking provides women innovators with resources, knowledge, and community support to overcome gender and cultural barriers, and advance their projects. Additionally, online platforms and networks enable rural women entrepreneurs to sell their products, share experiences, and foster cooperation, significantly contributing to their success. When it comes to finance, women innovators utilize a mix of private channels (personal savings, family loans) and public funding (local to EU levels) to support their projects. Due to challenges in obtaining public funding and venture capital, they often rely on creative strategies like community funding, volunteering, and personal funds, which highlight the unequal public fundings scheme. Lastly, the vastness of the impact of female-led innovation is shown in how they are transforming farms into multifunctional spaces that promote environmental sustainability, and offer diverse products and services to both locals, tourists and other consumers. These women not only provide valuable community services (including local economic resilience) but also act as role models, challenging gender stereotypes and encouraging the spread of innovative practices.

The practice abstracts follow the EIP-AGRI common format to ensure that the results are shared in a way that is attractive to end users. To foster dissemination, they will be uploaded on the FLIARA website, in a visually appealing manner, and will be included in the EIP-AGRI project database.

PRACTICE ABSTRACT 1

WHY WOMEN INNOVATE IN RURAL SWEDEN AND FINLAND

Insights from FLIARA's Nordic Baltic region case study comparative analysis show that while economic gain is usually assumed to be the primary reason for embarking upon innovation, this is not the case among women innovators in rural areas. Instead, the most important motivation is the desire to realize an idea—whether it is a new product, a service, or an innovative organizational form. Women are often driven by a strong passion for and belief in their ideas, not least because they see that their idea will help create a more sustainable society. The strong commitment to their ideas helps them overcome any challenges they face.

Ideas for innovation can emerge from four different areas:

- Their ideas are often linked to their **earlier education** or professional experience, which they use to create new career paths.
- In other cases, **hobbies are transformed into businesses**, particularly for those that use local natural resources.
- Many want to realize their ideas in **a specific rural place**, which could be where they currently live, or where they or their partner have their roots. The place is thus intimately connected with the innovation, providing specific opportunities as well as place-bound limitations.
- **Life changes**, such as leaving an unsatisfying job or starting a family, can also function as catalysts for the innovation journey.

It is important to recognize and legitimize the diverse motivations behind innovation, which extend beyond economic measures. Ends must be met, of course, but money by itself is not motivating. Personal development is a powerful motivator and should be acknowledged in the innovation journey of women-led initiatives in farming and in rural areas.

USEFUL LINKS

Realizing an idea based on the place: <https://fliara.eu/innovator/emilia-hildingsson/>

When growth just happens: <https://fliara.eu/innovator/anne-leena-pellikka/>

PRACTICE ABSTRACT 2

FINANCING RURAL AND FARM WOMEN-LED INNOVATION: A JIGSAW WITH MISSING PIECES?

Accessing the finance needed to support innovation development is crucial. FLIARA's case study comparative analysis also shows this clearly.

Women adapt and use many sources of finance. Women access finance through both private channels and public funding. Public funding can come through various sources from local to EU levels. Self-funding using personal savings and family loans are examples of private channels. There is also the issue of substituting finance with volunteer, as well as unpaid labour, which is unsustainable. Reliance on personal funding sources also limits women's potential to become innovators when they do not have access to personal funds.

Challenges accessing adequate finance. Women-led innovation takes a variety of approaches to raising needed finance showing the tenacity of women innovators. They also face significant challenges in accessing adequate finance. Improving the situation draws out a range of practical recommendations.

Tailored and innovative approaches appear needed. Depending on the type of innovation, private donations could also have relevance. Some women innovators have successfully accessed bank loans, while others are reluctant to. Alternative finance sources such as crowdfunding appear uncommon. Gaps in access to finance for particular stages of innovation development also emerged, highlighting the need for public finance to tailor its support to different innovation stages (e.g. scale-up, idea development).

Assess existing finance supports for improvements. When match funding is required alongside public funds, support could facilitate finding sources of match finance. The complexity and bureaucracy attached to sourcing finance is also a barrier and reducing this is important.

USEFUL LINKS

A German regional program incentivizing rural women's self-employment:
<https://fliara.eu/innovator/innovative-masnahmen-fur-frauen/>

See the experience of: <https://fliara.eu/innovator/lineke-lamfers/>;
<https://fliara.eu/innovator/petra-eckhardt-nancy-rietveld-and-barry-blommestein/>;
<https://fliara.eu/innovator/merel-gerritse-and-irma-brassinga/>

PRACTICE ABSTRACT 3

NETWORKING: A KEY FACILITATOR FOR RURAL AND FARM WOMEN-LED INNOVATION

Networking supports rural and farm women-led innovation. FLIARA's case study comparative analysis showed the availability of and engagement with strong networks was a key aspect for successful women-led innovation.

Networking provides diverse benefits. Networks support the innovation's start-up and development. More specific benefits include access to information, building skills, and connecting with potential mentors. Networks can also provide a wider source of support including toward self-empowerment.

Be part of a diverse range of networks. For example, this could mean networking through professional organisations as well as wider local community networks. Networking at a local level is important, but so are opportunities to expand regional, national and international networks.

Availability of networks and ability to network. This appears a key part of improving levels of women-led rural and farm innovation. Networking takes time therefore directly supporting women leading innovations to take part in networking appears important to increase women's capacity for networking.

Potential for specific targeted networking supports. New ideas could be women-led innovation networking vouchers that incentivise the activity and stipend payments for joining more formal and targeted networks. Networking opportunities must be available, which makes it important to support spaces and places where these opportunities are available, such as events and network meetings, as well as available infrastructure, such as community centres. Developing networks between operators working in the same territory and/or industry or supporting more informal networks to exchange knowledge and receive support also seems relevant.

USEFUL LINKS

See the experience of: <https://fliara.eu/innovator/a-womens-collective/>;
<https://fliara.eu/innovator/karen-brosnan/>; <https://fliara.eu/innovator/giulia-montepaone/>;
<https://fliara.eu/innovator/claudia-smolka/>; <https://fliara.eu/innovator/francesca-casaluci/>

PRACTICE ABSTRACT 4

WEB USE BY RURAL WOMEN INNOVATORS

Insights from FLIARA's case study comparative analysis show that women entrepreneurs living and working in rural areas use the web to sell their products to a significant extent. Online shops are particularly popular among women producing and selling handicrafts such as jewelry, pottery, clothes, or bags.

Aside from selling their handicrafts at local markets and shops or at their artisan workshop, online shops allow women to reach international clients and, at times, build partnerships with distributors in other countries. Moreover, customers can get in touch with the craftswoman directly (e.g. through online messages, emails or calls), asking her to produce tailor-made items according to their taste and needs.

The use of social media also appears to be very important in increasing the visibility of the business, as well as the support of social media managers. In addition, podcasts and short films about the business can be spread via social media and the company's website.

From these results, the following practical recommendations for enabling the spread of online shops are derived.

- **Broadband connection** should be enhanced in all rural areas, especially the most remote.
- Women entrepreneurs in rural areas could benefit from **targeted courses** about online sales and digital communication strategies to improve and expand their marketing skills.
- Opening an online shop also requires learning new techniques and creating **new mindsets around cyber security** thereby reducing vulnerability to cyber-attack.

USEFUL LINKS

See the experiences of: <https://fliara.eu/innovator/flavia-amato/>; <https://fliara.eu/innovator/aoife-noone/>; <https://fliara.eu/innovator/inge-vleemingh-and-heimen-vos/>; <https://fliara.eu/innovator/sarah-khoudja/>; <https://fliara.eu/innovator/alex-van-hootegeem/>

PRACTICE ABSTRACT 5

WOMEN-LED INNOVATION IN MULTIFUNCTIONAL FARMING

Insights from FLIARA's case study comparative analysis show that women-led innovation in farming often entails offering different farm-related activities and services, targeting both the local population and tourists. In this way, farms come to signify much more than their agricultural production: they become places where people reconnect to agriculture, and to nature in general.

Among the services offered are farm-based restaurants and accommodation, kindergartens for children of different ages, educational workshops and experiences for adults and children, cooking workshops, guided walks with animals, in-loco market and shops. Often, part of the offer targets specifically vulnerable groups such as disabled people.

By engaging in multifunctional farming, women:

- 1) **spread awareness about ethical and healthy ways of producing and consuming food.**
- 2) **enhance social inclusion**, while collaborating with schools and other local associations.
- 3) **increase and diversify their income**, often employing local professionals such as teachers and guides and establishing partnerships with schools and tourist agencies.

Imagining and introducing new services on the farm makes it possible to use a variety of skills and knowledge (not just agricultural).

Establishing collaborations with local institutions (e.g. schools, social welfare centres) could be useful to foster the use of the new services.

Women could also benefit from targeted economic support (e.g. through some CAP measures) and LAGs support.

USEFUL LINKS

See the experiences of: <https://fliara.eu/innovator/luigia-e-simona-soffritti/>;
<https://fliara.eu/innovator/noora-pakonen-laura-huusko/>;
<https://fliara.eu/innovator/stefania-lusuardi/>; <https://fliara.eu/innovator/belinda-schwarz-wittigschlager/>;
<https://fliara.eu/innovator/daniella-de-winter-and-bart-pijnenburg/>;
<https://fliara.eu/innovator/sofia-de-matteis/>

PRACTICE ABSTRACT 6

INNOVATING TO ENHANCE ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY IN FARMING

Insights from FLIARA's case study comparative analysis show that across the EU women innovators display a high interest in developing farming projects that foreground environmental sustainability.

This means that many chose to practice organic, biodynamic or regenerative farming, avoiding chemicals and respecting nature's rhythms. Moreover, they often chose to preserve local traditional crops and breeds which are considered more sustainable and better suited to the local environment. This allows them to take care of soil health and animal wellbeing.

The majority of the interviewed women innovators in farming, even those holding an agricultural degree, have learned how to practice alternative forms of agriculture through courses offered by informal networks of organic farmers, or they gained knowledge and experience by doing and experimenting.

Improving training programs and AKIS services to support these sustainable forms of agriculture, especially in the context of small farms, appears fundamental.

Also, agricultural schools could offer more varied courses on these types of agriculture. A best practice is the Warmonderhof - a small-scale school in the Netherlands - which provides training, education, teaching facilities, internships, and practical testing on organic and biodynamic farming methods.

Promoting the visibility of these farms, through national campaigns, videos and podcasts to show the opportunities related to this model of agriculture is another useful action to sensitise other (women) farmers to engage in sustainable environmental agriculture.

USEFUL LINKS

See the experiences of: <https://fliara.eu/innovator/annette-harberink/>;
<https://fliara.eu/innovator/blatnaid-gallagher/>; <https://fliara.eu/innovator/meike-hollnaicher/>;
<https://fliara.eu/innovator/karin-malmgren/>; <https://fliara.eu/innovator/agnes-de-boer/>

PRACTICE ABSTRACT 7

INNOVATION PATHWAYS TO SUCCESS IN RURAL AREAS

Insights from FLIARA's case study comparative analysis show that women innovators in rural areas use many different pathways and practices to success and there are no clear patterns. The women build their required knowledge and secure financial means step by step, but the nature and scope of these steps varied widely. Three successful strategies for realizing innovations in rural areas:

Creative strategies for funding. The women innovators in rural areas use creative strategies to fund their projects because public funding and venture capital is often difficult to obtain. Most support systems are geared towards large, STEM-focused businesses, often excluding non-profit organizations and non-economic activities, as well as social enterprises. Instead, the women use a combination of community funding, family support, volunteering and personal funds to sustain their projects. External financial support is typically sought later to expand existing activities.

Networking. Networks play a crucial role in connecting women innovators with stakeholders and spreading awareness about their projects. Engaging in networks enables the women to access resources, knowledge, and build trust, helping them to overcome gender and cultural conventions. These networks help foster a sense of community and support the provision of local services to advance their projects.

High tech and low tech. Some women innovators have developed innovative technological solutions tailored to their specific contexts. On the other hand, some women prefer to rely on technological innovations and use low-tech solutions. However, all women innovators use digital technology in their innovations as most women have well-designed websites and social media pages for marketing and expanding networks, targeting both local and international audiences.

USEFUL LINKS

See the experience of: <https://fliara.eu/innovator/evelien-kamphuis/>

Working with volunteers: <https://fliara.eu/innovator/petra-matos/>

Focusing on a low-tech solution: <https://fliara.eu/innovator/annelies-svensson/>

PRACTICE ABSTRACT 8

BUILDING CONFIDENCE AND SELF-ESTEEM IN RURAL WOMEN INNOVATORS

Insights from FLIARA's case study comparative analysis show that beside the women's motivation, ideas, knowledge, education etc. they also need support in building confidence and self-esteem for realization of their ideas and development of innovations. This need is often invisible, but it emerged as a recurring theme in several interviews.

We recommend the following steps/fields to empower rural women innovators, enhancing their confidence and self-esteem:

Establish a support network. Our findings highlight the importance of peer groups where women can share challenges and successes. These networks provide emotional support and foster resilience, showing women they are not alone. Those networks also offer mutual learning and exchanges of life experiences related to their innovations.

Promote skill-building workshops. Our findings reveal that accessible, hands-on workshops focused on digital skills, sustainable practices, business development, and leadership are essential. Such structured learning experiences empower women by boosting competence and self-esteem.

Showcase success stories. Local, regional and national success stories of women innovators demonstrate the potential to overcome challenges, providing inspiration and reinforcing self-esteem. FLIARA innovation Ambassadors demonstrate the empowerment of rural women.

Encourage flexible roles and life balance: Our research underscores the need for adaptable work models that respect personal time and family responsibilities. This reduces burnout and enhances long-term commitment.

These and other similar evidence-based recommendations provide rural women with practical steps to build self-confidence and capacities to realize impactful innovations.

USEFUL LINKS

Strong support network: <https://fliara.eu/innovator/nina-arnus-anka-pintar/>

FLIARA Ambassadors as a showcase: <https://fliara.eu/ambassadors/>

PRACTICE ABSTRACT 9

LEADER/CLLD: A SUPPORTIVE ENVIRONMENT FOR WOMEN'S INNOVATIONS IN RURAL AREAS

Insights from FLIARA's case study comparative analysis show that the delivery of LEADER/CLLD (Community-Led Local Development) as a method, approach, and a measure/intervention of rural development policy opened up opportunities and set up a supportive environment for female innovation in agriculture and in rural areas.

Raising visibility of women in rural areas. The LAGs (local action group), introduced by the implementation of LEADER/CLLD, have increased the visibility of rural women in terms of participation – their active involvement in community activities, projects and initiatives, and decision-making.

Seed investment. LEADER/CLLD funds are modest, but stimulating as seed investments in rural communities, rural localities and rural fabrics – quite often putting at the forefront the social innovation which is a strong field of rural women entrepreneurship.

Cooperation and networking are two of seven LEADER principles, both of which are deeply embedded in rural women's entrepreneurship. Individual and collaborative networks are created amongst private, public and civil sectors, between formal and informal associations and are contributing to bonding, bridging and linking social capital in rural areas.

Operational interface. National Rural Development Networks could serve as an operational interface, functioning as a node in which support for joint learning and innovation is operationalized, awhile connecting different levels of decision-makers, advocating for rural interests and functioning as a good network broker.

Reflexive discourses. Frequent reflexive discourses among multiple rural development stakeholders are crucial for continuous learning, innovation and effective rural policymaking.

USEFUL LINKS

See the experiences of: <https://fliara.eu/innovator/anna-carkova/> and <https://elard.eu>

Book on LEADER delivery in Slovenia: <https://doi.org/10.4312/9789612970031>

PRACTICE ABSTRACT 10

INSPIRING CHANGE: SCALING YOUR INNOVATION BY IMITATION

Insights from FLIARA's case study comparative analysis show that women-led innovations in farming and rural areas have a substantial impact on the local level – providing products and services important for the local community, providing a livelihood for the innovators and their employees, and renegotiating attitudes towards sustainability and the role of women in society. Engaged in typically labour-intensive industries such as tourism, events, or artisan foods, women innovators are often happy with maintaining a manageable size and serving a local market. They may not have the growth ambitions common in technical fields, but they are eager to see their sustainable innovation expand to other contexts through various forms of *imitation*, even if this may not be financially rewarding.

Successful strategies for scaling by imitation:

Being a role model. By simply doing what they do, the innovators act as role models, and in doing so they show that women can play a significant role in rural businesses, associations, and communities. By being leaders, they challenge gender stereotypes and pave the way for other innovative women in their communities and beyond.

Spreading the word. They are innovative by actively encouraging imitation through study visits, internships, and by cooperating with other women. By joining or creating women's networks and focusing on women suppliers and customers, they empower women and strengthen female cooperation.

Welcoming copy-cats. The women are positively inclined to copy-cats since they are eager for their innovation to spread. The innovation being copied extends beyond a specific product or service, including an innovative philosophy of the business, hiring practices, or any context-specific model developed.

USEFUL LINKS

Using copy-cats as a business model: <https://fliara.eu/innovator/alexandra-larsson/> and <https://fliara.eu/innovator/malin-axelsson/>

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